

COMPARING INERTIAL MOTION SENSORS FOR CAPTURING HUMAN MICROMOTION

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a study of the noise level of accelerometer data from a mobile phone compared to three commercially available IMU-based devices (AX3, Equivital, and Movesense) and an infrared motion capture system (Qualisys). The sensors are compared in static positions and for measuring human micromotion, with larger motion sequences as reference. The measurements show that all but one of the IMU-based devices capture motion with an accuracy and precision that is far below human micromotion. However, their data and representations differ, so care should be taken when comparing data between devices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Until recently, (music) researchers had to rely on controlled laboratory settings and high-end equipment to capture detailed human motion and physiology. Today’s mobile phones are powerful devices with sensors that can measure light, sound, temperature, and various motion data. The latter is typically recorded with inertial measurement units (IMUs), which have seen decades of development for commercial use in industries such as sports, fitness, military and healthcare. Today, such sensors are readily available in mobile phones, allowing music researchers to capture data for both analysis and creative applications.

At RITMO, we conduct research on a variety of music-related body motion, from detailed studies of musicians’ performance technique to the small- and large-scale motion of people experiencing music. Many studies use state-of-the-art equipment in our labs, but we increasingly research music performers and perceivers in real-world settings. This includes using various mobile sensing devices and has led to our interest in exploring mobile phones for data collection. Using participants’ mobile phones in studies allows for scaling motion-based data collection to hundreds and possibly thousands of people.

We have over the years developed an experimental paradigm based on measuring people’s micromotion when asked to stand or sit still [1–3]. Micromotion is here defined as the tiniest motion observable when people try not to move. In

Figure 1. An illustration of the experimental setup used in this study. Human micromotion was captured from a person standing still for 10 minutes with a mobile phone hanging around the neck and multiple IMU-based sensor devices placed close to the location of the phone. An average image (left) and average motion image (middle) show that the person moved very little during the standstill session. The motiongram (right) shows the spatiotemporal distribution (time runs from left to right) and the periodic swaying of the upper body.

our latest concert experiments, we have tried to capture audiences’ physical response to music by capturing their micromotion through mobile phones hanging on their chest. However, this raises questions about whether sensor data obtained from mobile phones is as viable as that recorded on more sophisticated systems—namely, high-resolution wearable sensors, motion capture, and video recordings.

In this paper, we aim to answer the following questions:

1. What is the noise level of the IMU in a mobile phone, and can it reliably capture human micromotion?
2. How do the mobile phone IMU data compare to commercially available IMU-based motion capture devices?
3. How do IMU data compare to the motion features extracted from a regular video recording and a marker-based infrared optical motion capture system?

Our target application is music research, but these questions are valid for other research disciplines using IMUs.

2. BACKGROUND

There has been a growing interest in studies of music-related body motion over the last decades [4–8]. Most of these are studies on relatively large-scale body motion. However,

there are also studies investigating how music can induce micromotion when people try to stand still [1–3, 9, 10].

Human micromotion is largely influenced by internal rhythmic processes of the human body, such as respiration and heartbeat [11, 12]. Certain external factors, such as temperature, also contribute; a low temperature could cause shivering. The micromotion observed when people stand still is often the result of corrective feedback mechanisms in the body that ensure a specific posture, even when the subject is in a still-standing position [13]. Blinking is another involuntary reflex, which causes a micromotion based on feedback, through which the body ensures that the eyes do not dry out from prolonged contact with the air [14, 15].

Numerous sensor types and systems exist for measuring music-related body motion [16], and many of these also work well for musical practice [17]. Marker-based motion capture systems based on infrared cameras are often considered state-of-the-art when it comes to tracking position with high accuracy and precision. We have previously confirmed that higher-end systems generally perform better than mid-range systems [18] and that newer mid-range systems may be comparable to older high-end systems [19].

Camera-based motion capture systems generally work well in laboratories but are challenging to use in real-world settings. If relative position tracking is sufficient, systems based on inertial measurement units (IMUs) are beneficial. IMUs usually have three sensors: a 3D accelerometer, a 3D gyroscope, and a 3D magnetometer [20]. Accelerometers are based on the gravitational pull and, therefore, measure the tilt of a device with respect to the surface of the Earth. Gyroscopes measure angular motion or rotation. Magnetometers determine the orientation of a device by measuring the strength of the magnetic field on each of the three axes. Together, these three sensors in an IMU can be used to calculate the linear acceleration of an object or body part.

We have previously shown that inertial tracking can compare to an optical motion capture system in real-world dance research [21]. We have also shown that the inertial sensors of consumer devices provide reliable relative motion tracking, although they experience considerable drift if one tries to estimate position [22]. Comparisons of three different phone brands show that the accelerometer data is comparable across devices and with similar accuracy to a high-end optical motion capture system [23]. All these studies were based on large-scale body motion. Less is known about how well various IMU-based motion tracking systems capture human micromotion.

3. EXPERIMENT

The experiment reported in this paper focused on the raw accelerometer data of mobile phones and IMU-based motion capture devices. The idea was to investigate the noise level of the devices by recording them while lying still (“ground truth”) and compare this to data of human micromotion captured of a subject standing still on the floor. We also recorded some larger-scale motion sequences for reference.

Figure 2. The placement of sensors: the mobile phone hang in a strap around the neck with reflective markers attached to each top corner. The Equival system was mounted on a vest with shoulder straps and the Movesense sensor (white sensor) was attached to a chest belt. The AX3 sensor was placed in a small pocket behind the mobile phone.

3.1 Devices

We recorded the motion of a person wearing various IMU-based motion capture devices simultaneously, including a mobile phone attached to a case hanging from a cord around the person’s neck (Figure 2). This way, the sensors were all roughly in the same position on the body. In addition to the sensor-based systems, we used an infrared motion capture system and a video camera to capture the person’s motion.

3.1.1 Mobile Phone

A Samsung Galaxy S21 Ultra mobile phone was used to capture mobile phone sensor data using the Android app Physics Toolbox Sensor Suite¹ by Vieyra Software (version 2023.01.21). The phone was set to capture all sensors at the maximum rate, including data from the accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer, as well as light and sound pressure levels. The app also performed sensor fusion, storing linear acceleration and some other features. However, in this paper, only the raw accelerometer data will be assessed. The sample rate for these measurements varied from under 20 Hz to over 40 Hz. For analyses of spectral information, each excerpt was linearly resampled at a stable rate close to the local average.

3.1.2 Wearable Sensors

Three commercially available IMU-based wearable sensor systems were used in the study:

¹ <https://www.vieyrasoftware.net/>

- Axivity AX3² is a simple data-logging accelerometer. It records with a 13-bit resolution and the sensitivity was set to $\pm 8 g$ and the sampling rate to 200 Hz for this experiment.
- Equivital eq02+ LifeMonitor³ is a multiparameter physiological data capture device combining a wearable 2-channel ECG, respiration monitor, thermometer, and tri-axial accelerometer. The data was captured on-device for this experiment, with a 12-bit resolution and 25.6 Hz for the accelerometry.
- Movesense Flash⁴ is a compact sensor with a 1-channel ECG and IMU. The data was captured over Bluetooth through its phone application during this experiment. The accelerometer was captured at 208 Hz with a sensitivity of $\pm 8 g$.

The devices all have different specifications for the accelerometers, which indicates the use of different IMU chip components inside the devices or different data processing methods.

3.1.3 Infrared Motion Capture

The infrared motion capture recording was conducted using a Qualisys system with nine Oqus 300 cameras pointing at the calibrated three-dimensional space surrounding the subject. Three reflective markers were placed on the subject: one on the top of the head and two on the top corners of the mobile phone hanging from the neck.

3.1.4 Video Recording

A GoPro Max was used to record a 360-degree video of the space in 5K resolution. For motion analysis, a 2D video image of 500×1600 pixels was cropped out of the 360-degree video. The camera was mounted on a tripod to ensure that the pixels making up the subject's image were the only ones that moved.

3.2 Procedure

The noise level was captured from two static positions: (1) all sensors lying on the floor and (2) all sensors lying on a table. We were curious whether the placement on a table would affect the sensors differently than being placed on the floor due to either metal interference or building vibrations. These recordings would give an idea of the amount of noise to expect in the motion data obtained from the non-static variations of the experiment involving the standstill micromotion.

Human micromotion was captured from a subject wearing all sensor devices and standing still twice, 10 minutes each time. This is sufficient time to let the subject rest and pick up a regular breathing pattern [3, 10].

At the end of the standstill session, the subject also performed some motion exercises reflecting the different body

Figure 3. Motion history images illustrating the five motion exercises. From left: (1) squats, (2) upper-body rotation, (3) forward-bending, (4) sideways swaying, (5) “air violin.”

planes: (1) squats, (2) upper-body rotation, (3) forward-bending, (4) sideways swaying, (5) “air violin.” Each exercise was performed ten times to allow for comparison (Figure 3).

3.3 Analysis

Data were exported from the respective devices and imported into Jupyter Notebooks for processing in Python using a combination of custom-made scripts and functions from the Musical Gestures Toolbox [24].⁵

The four devices report values in different scales. We calculated the average total acceleration in the floor recording in each device's reported units to check the different scales. In this condition, the main force acting on each device is gravity. No matter the device's orientation, the acceleration norm should equal g , which at 60 degrees near sea level should be about 9.818 m/s^2 .

4. RESULTS

4.1 Noise level

Figure 4 shows plots of the accelerometer data from one of the recordings when the phone was lying still on the floor. It shows that the noise level is consistent over time and uniform across the three axes. The motion spectrogram does not reveal energy in any particular frequency bands.

As seen in Figure 5, human micromotion is considerably larger than the noise level of the phone. Here the X -axis represents vertical motion, which typically moves less than the two other axes. As expected, most motion can be found in the anterior–posterior motion (in the transversal plane); the body typically sways more back and forth since the feet stabilize sideways. The motion spectrogram reveals resonant frequency components in the frequency range of the pulse (around 80 bpm) and respiration.

For comparison, Figure 6 shows how the data looks for larger-scale motion sequences performed in the different axes.

4.2 Device comparison

Table 1 summarizes some findings from comparing the different devices. It is interesting to see how effective sampling rates differ between devices. The phone was set to record at maximum speed and output a file stored at approximately 200 Hz. However, this sampling rate is based

⁵ Source code is available from <https://github.com/fourMs/ambient/tree/main/SMC2023> and data from <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/WB7A3>

²<https://axivity.com/product/ax3>

³<https://equivital.com/products/eq02-lifemonitor>

⁴<https://www.movesense.com/product/movesense-flash/>

Figure 4. Plots of accelerometer data from the mobile phone lying still on the floor. Time series plots (top), spatial plots (middle), spectrogram of accelerometer data linearly interpolated to 20 Hz (bottom).

Signal	Hz	X	Y	Z	g
AX3	194.9	-0.010	0.001	-1.010	1.010
Equivaltal	25.6	76.47	972.4	-52.80	976.8
Movesense	210.6	-0.138	0.126	9.741	9.743
Phone	20.04	0.001	-0.009	1.006	1.006

Table 1. Average sample rates, dimensional averages, and gravity in original device units from four accelerometers during the static floor measurements. These g values are used to standardise units between devices to $g = 9.818$ for the noise comparison.

on capturing multiple sensors that probably run at different sampling rates. So when removing duplicates for the accelerometer data, we only get an effective sampling rate ranging from 13 to 40 Hz.

During the static conditions, gravity was the principal acceleration force on each device, allowing us to compare the units recorded on these devices when lying on the floor or table. At Oslo’s longitude and elevation, gravity is estimated to be $g = 9.818m/s^2$. When gravity is estimated in each device’s native units, we see a range of normalisation strategies. The Movesense reported float values in approximate m/s^2 , while the AX3 and phone recordings were normalised to set gravity to 1.0. The Equivaltal system recorded values in integers and appears to scale m/s^2 up with a factor of 100 to maintain usable precision.

To make the recordings comparable, all the accelerometer measurements were scaled to m/s^2 using Oslo’s local

Figure 5. Plots of accelerometer data from the mobile phone hanging around the neck of a person standing still for 10 minutes. Spectrogram from 16 Hz resampling of normalised acceleration.

gravity constant. Figure 7 shows examples of normed jerk values (m/s^3 , removing the gravity constant) from each device in one static and standing condition. Table 2 reports the statistics of the normed jerk of these devices in four recording conditions (two static and two micromotion), demonstrating the impact of their respective noise floors. It is interesting that the mobile phone has the lowest noise level in the static conditions.

While the motion of all devices were effectively identical for the static condition, their different placements on the body during the standstill conditions have to be considered when interpreting the micromotion data. For example, the Movesense sensor appears to have captured more cardiac-related motion from its position over the diaphragm than the phone hung slightly higher on the chest. However, the low noise and sample rates make these displacements more noticeable. The most important finding here is that the noise level of the mobile phone is considerably lower than the micromotion data. On the other hand, the noise level of the AX3 appears to have effectively obliterated any trace of micromotion.

4.3 IMU versus infrared mocap

To compare IMU data to Qualisys, we had to take the second derivative of position to find the acceleration. This acceleration is not directly comparable to the accelerometer data from the IMUs—which measure gravitational pull and not linear acceleration—but the magnitudes are com-

	Floor (static)	Table (static)	Standing 1 (body)	Standing 2 (body)
AX3	0.124 (0.084, Mx 0.50)	0.094 (0.085, Mx 0.48)	0.085 (0.086, Mx 0.46)	0.103 (0.087, Mx 0.50)
Equivital	0.064 (0.029, Mx 0.18)	0.062 (0.029, Mx 0.17)	0.079 (0.037, Mx 0.24)	0.088 (0.045, Mx 0.29)
Movesense	0.047 (0.020, Mx 0.16)	0.047 (0.020, Mx 0.16)	0.070 (0.053, Mx 0.71)	0.059 (0.030, Mx 0.24)
Phone	0.031 (0.012, Mx 0.15)	0.027 (0.011, Mx 0.06)	0.099 (0.065, Mx 0.40)	0.066 (0.043, Mx 0.35)

Table 2. Average (standard deviation, and maximum) samplewise magnitude of change on accelerometer measurements ($g = 9.818m/s^2$) in four devices for 120 s in four conditions. The lowest values are marked in bold font.

Figure 6. Plots of accelerometer data from the mobile phone hanging around a person’s neck performing five different motion sequences. Spectrogram from 50 Hz resampling of normalised acceleration.

Figure 7. Sample-wise Quantity of Motion (normalised to g) for 10 seconds from the four accelerometers in static (floor) and micromotion (standing1) conditions.

Figure 8. Z-normalized change in position in three dimensions for head and phone markers across the same 10-second period as the standing plots (right) of Figure 7.

parable. We have previously confirmed that this system has a noise level at a magnitude lower than human micromotion [18].

Figure 8 shows plots of relative position change for markers on the subject’s head and phone during 10 seconds of standstill. Each dimension was z-normalised for plotting purposes, resulting in the smaller vertical displacement of the head showing greater noise proportional to the signal. Despite differences in scale of displacement, the low frequency oscillation of the wearer’s respiratory cycle is captured through both the phone motion on the chest (vertical, anterior–posterior) and the head motion (anterior–posterior). Overall, the phone moved more during the 10-second example period than the head (norm of 3D phone accelerations $M = 1.256m/s^2$; norm of 3D head acceleration $M = .749m/s^2$), presumably because the phone was more strongly affected by breathing. This comparison helps gauge the viability of using head markers instead of torso markers for standstill motion studies.

4.4 IMU versus video recordings

Figure 9 shows a plot of the quantity of motion—calculated as the sum of active pixels in a frame-differenced motion video—of a video recording shot of the first standstill session (as depicted in Figure 1). In general, we would not expect to be able to pick up micromotion with sufficient quality from a video camera. The plot of the whole sequence shows spikes coming from the camera’s buffering at regular intervals. However, the close-up of a 10-second segment shows that the camera can detect micromotion

Figure 9. Quantity of motion calculated as the active pixels in a frame-differenced video recording. Full recording (top) and a 10-second excerpt (bottom).

features. More investigation must be done to relate these measurements to the accelerometer data.

5. CONCLUSION

From the data captured in the present study, we can conclude the following:

- The noise level of the IMU in a mobile phone is better than we expected and much lower than human micromotion. However, this data is only from one phone, so it would be relevant to compare data from more mobile phones in future research.
- Commercially available IMU-based sensor devices use different sensors and capture data with different sensitivities, sampling rates, and resolutions. Most importantly, they all report data differently when it comes to g . This could lead to confusion among researchers and make comparing results from different studies difficult.
- The same motion trends found in the IMU-based devices can be found in data from an optical motion capture system. Not surprisingly, regular video recordings are not very good at capturing human micromotion when compared to dedicated devices and systems.

Our study has revealed that it is difficult to find reliable information about the sensors in commercial devices. This makes it challenging to compare them because they all behave differently. Still, the noise levels (except for AX3) are generally capable of capturing human micromotion and should be fine for any type of larger-scale motion. We are particularly impressed by the capabilities of the mobile phone.

There are many limitations of the current study. The positioning and orientation of wearable sensors matter. In this study, the AX3 was hung around the neck of the subject together with the mobile phone, the Equival was worn on the proprietary sensor vest, and the Movesense was snapped onto a belt around the chest. Therefore, the differing ways of how the sensors were worn also contribute to human-added noise.

In the future, we will run studies that compare different brands and types of mobile phones to get better comparative data. We will also analyse the other data types captured during this experiment, including the respiration and pulse data.

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